

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF THE COUNTRY'S EXIT FROM THE "POVERTY TRAP" AND ITS USE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article is proposed a simple theoretical model to study the dynamics of an economy in which individuals move out of poverty trap. These dynamics are characterized by growth acceleration and temporarily growing inequalities. We provide stylized facts based on income distribution data that suggest that many recent acceleration episodes fit our theoretical predictions. Although poverty exits may result from income growth we find a number of cases of autonomous poverty exits. These poverty exits may have two different causes: successful reforms creating more job opportunities for the poor and successful pro-poor transfer policies.

Key words: Economic growth, poverty, policy reform, debt relief.

The term poverty trap is used in the literature at different levels of aggregation, from the individual or household microeconomic level to the macroeconomic or countrywide level. In this regard, we can refer interested readers to recent surveys of this literature in Barrett and Carter , who consider mainly microeconomic aspects, and Kraay and McKenzie , who also discuss the available evidence at the aggregate level. Most microeconomic models of the poverty trap rely on particular assumptions regarding technology that are complemented by capital or labor market imperfections. A central assumption is that individuals choose between traditional subsistence activities and modern entrepreneurial activities that require a fixed investment. Moving out of the poverty trap would imply investing in modern tools of production, which is prevented by risk-aversion and imperfections in the capital market. Carter and Barrett investigate this possibility and define what they call a Micawber threshold separating situations in which individuals are too poor to accumulate assets that would help them invest in improved methods of production from situations in which such investment is feasible. In their research, Aghion and Bolton study the underlying capital market model, whereas Banerjee and Newman study the consequences on occupational choices (self-employment vs. contractual employment). Dasgupta and Ray introduce another possible cause of poverty traps that relies on the efficiency wage model. In their model, the poverty trap arises from the low employability of the poor, which locks them into unemployment and poverty. Other theories regarding the poverty trap are based on specific behavioral assumptions. For instance, Moav and Neeman propose a model in which the poor spend part of their income in conspicuous consumption

as a means of improving their social status. Such conspicuous consumption prevents them from saving and helps keep them in poverty. Although these theoretical models of poverty traps have attracted substantial attention, a consensus can hardly be reached regarding the empirical relevance of such models, notably at the macroeconomic level. Kraay and McKenzie argue that many developing countries have experienced similar or more rapid growth than the US in recent decades, implying that they should at some point have crossed any poverty trap threshold. In particular, these authors consider that the growth accelerations observed by Hausmann et al. well with the predictions from the poverty trap theories.

Chronic poverty and justice Chronic poverty is a key policy challenge of the 21st Century. Hundreds of millions of people exist in conditions of extreme deprivation throughout much or all of their lives. The chronically poor are unable to develop their personal capabilities or provide a good start in life for their children, and often die prematurely of preventable causes. While poverty has been a key concern of national governments for decades, even centuries in some countries, there are now, for the first time, global frameworks for poverty reduction, to which governments and international agencies are largely committed. The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Poverty Reduction Strategies (PRSs), alongside a number of important rights charters, have increased the visibility of the poor. Their wellbeing is increasingly a matter of global concern. However, neither the MDGs nor most PRSs currently consider the chronically poor to a sufficient degree. Even achieving the first MDG by 2015 would still leave some 800 million people living in absolute poverty and deprivation – many of whom would be chronically poor. And there is only one MDG – achieving universal primary education – for which the chronically poor must be effectively included for the goal to be met.¹ The achievement of the other goals is currently measured against mean population figures (where there are targets at all), and therefore can be met by addressing the needs of those who are relatively easy and inexpensive for policy instruments to reach, i.e. those closest to the poverty line and most accessible.

Policies against chronic poverty – Preventing entries and promoting exits. Our integrated policy set tackles the multiple and overlapping causes of chronic poverty through preventing entries into poverty, and through promoting exits from poverty. This is important, because the factors causing people to slip into poverty are not always the mirror image of those required to enable them to escape. In this respect, promoting ways out of poverty generally requires a

different combination of strategies to those required for preventing downward mobility. Isolating the reasons for entry into, and exit from poverty, is not an easy task. The collection and analysis of good quality longitudinal quantitative and qualitative data is the best method, with a combination of panel surveys and life histories being particularly effective.³⁵ The importance of distinguishing between the factors that cause entries, and those that precipitate exits, can be illustrated through Anirudh Krishna's work – which relied on participatory methods – in rural locations in Asia, subSaharan Africa and Latin America.³⁶ Krishna's work highlights how ill health and the costs of healthcare are overwhelmingly the single most important reason why households enter into poverty. Health shocks reduce the income-earning capacity of the household, and increase expenditure. Social expenditures on marriages and funerals are also often associated with descents into poverty. Escapes, by contrast, are most commonly associated with income diversification (on and off the farm), and access to employment and the social networks (often kin-based) that provide information about such jobs. Overall, Krishna suggests that policies on health services, social protection, and limiting the impact of one-off social expenditures are most likely to limit descents, while policies supporting diversification, urbanisation, and informal sector employment are most likely to facilitate escapes. Different policy approaches are clearly required to address downward mobility into poverty and upward mobility out of poverty. Each of the key policies featured in this report addresses both, but with different emphases. For example, social protection clearly protects against downward mobility (through providing a buffer against shocks), but can also provide a springboard for exiting poverty (through allowing investments in assets and livelihood strategies). In terms of public services, post-primary education mainly promotes exits – if not in this generation, then in the next – while the better provision of reproductive health services can help both to prevent entries and to promote exits.

In the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the fight against poverty was identified as a priority task. It was emphasized that "poverty reduction requires the implementation of a comprehensive economic and social policy - from stimulating entrepreneurial activity to mobilizing the abilities and potential of the population, creating new jobs".

Economic laws show that "poverty reproduces poverty". This happens for several reasons. First, poor countries cannot afford to spend enough to maintain affordable, free, and high-quality health care and education, and poor people

cannot afford to pay for adequate private services. As a result, less educated and less healthy poor people cannot get out of poverty because of the low quality of human potential. Secondly, the poorer the population, the lower the effective demand, the lower the capacity of the consumer market, and, accordingly, the incentives for the development of industry, agriculture and, especially, services. This, in turn, constrains the development of the economy, reduces budget revenues and in a closed cycle - the possibility of social support for the poor. Thirdly, the mentality of people from poor families often differs from those of wealthier families. Due to the above reasons, lesser people from poor families are with creative and entrepreneurial thinking. The crime rate among people from poor families is generally higher.

Foreign experiences. Social protection is a government policy, a package of measures and programs aimed at reducing poverty and inequality, and increasing the well-being of socially vulnerable groups of the population. The organized system of social protection of the state in the Western world began to enjoy success at the beginning of the 20th century - the period of the creation of social security systems in Germany and Great Britain, and a little later in the USA - during the Great Depression. If 100 years ago, systems of social protection of the population officially existed only in a few countries, today they are practically everywhere. The logic, tools and mechanisms for applying such schemes differ as countries seek to build social protection systems based on their capabilities, national conditions and priorities. Institutions of social support for the population play an important role in overcoming poverty, which are designed not only to help financially but also to help the most vulnerable groups get out of poverty. In developed countries, since the 1990s social assistance in the form of grants began to be provided with mandatory requirements for the involvement of its recipients in legal entrepreneurship. In those countries where such practices were used (Korea, US, New Zealand, UK and others.) active engagement of the population on employment was observed. The results of various studies show that a more accurate assessment of the needs of the beneficiary, which is based not only on the level of his income but also taking into account other unrecorded incomes provides more effective tools in terms of poverty alleviation. This mechanism of comprehensive criteria includes a comparison of the declarations of data with data of tax and other public authorities. These changes in the system of providing targeted social assistance is partly a factor of reducing official poverty rates in countries such as Austria, Belgium, Australia, Canada, Czech Republic, Denmark, etc. in the mid-2000s.

Different countries use different schemes to reduce poverty rates. The Swedish model considers the fulfillment of two goals: full employment and income equalization. In this Scandinavian country, they prefer to retrain the unemployed and return them to work in demanded areas. China has adopted a wide range of measures aimed at rural development, including reforms in the agricultural sector, along with land reforms in rural areas. In the Czech Republic in addition to basic assistance to the poor, an emphasis is placed on assistance in natural form and cash compensation as an additional tool to support the poor. In the United States, assistance to the poor is provided within the framework of special programs that cover 15% to 20% of the population. In-kind assistance has become widespread: food stamps, low-cost housing, medical care of elderly and o early childhood care and others. For the conditions of Uzbekistan, the most acceptable comprehensive approach to poverty reduction should be aimed at engaging as many working-age populations in employment, while simultaneously defining a package of state social support that will help those in need below the poverty line to get out of poverty trap. At the same time, in the conditions of the impossibility of immediate eradication of poverty, it is recommended to gradually implement measures in the field of ensuring the social protection of the poor, creating additional opportunities for earning stable income and improving human capital.

Social Model. Uzbekistan belongs to socially oriented countries. In such countries, there is a significant presence of the state in the life of society, which implies a wide range of social obligations of the state in front of its citizens. This makes it necessary to provide state support to socially vulnerable groups of society. Strong social policy, this means that state institutions carry out a certain redistribution of public goods in favor of the least protected and most vulnerable members of society. For all these years in Uzbekistan, unlike many other countries, the need for a strong social policy has not been questioned. That is, it can be stated that Uzbekistan a priori has chosen a model of state policy that corresponds to the concept of social justice. For thousands of years, a traditional worldview was formed on our land that people should help each other, and the poor and the vulnerable, who are in difficult life situations, should receive support from those who can provide it: from neighbors, from society. Our social contract is based on these centuries-old principles of public morality.

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